

United States PhD Admission

Application process in a nutshell *

Ibrahim Mirza †

Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, TN, United States

Abstract

PhD admission is also called graduate school admission and PhD students are usually called graduate (in short "grad") students in the United States. Graduate school application process could be complicated as well as lengthy, specifically for international applicants. This article unfolds the essential steps in the application process and gives a bird's eye view on the entire admission process in a lucid manner. Essential qualifications, required exams, stipend, statement of purpose, letter of recommendation, VISA process, pre-arrival instructions etc are briefly described.

Application Documents

Academic cycle in the US universities follow semester system as :

- Fall semester (August - December)
- Spring semester (January - May)
- Summer semester (June - July)

Normally graduate students are admitted in the fall semester. Students have to apply in the preceding year. Last dates to PhD admission in most US universities for the fall semester typically varies between December 01 to January 15. All application materials are submitted before this date.

*Disclaimer : for introductory information only. This article may not include all necessary application steps. Applicants must verify the information presented in this article from the university they want to apply for and will follow the university guidelines.

†ibm.lhcms@gmail.com

Students should make a list of universities they want to apply to. For this purpose, visit (your subject) department website of the US universities and find the available research areas of your interest in the department and shortlist a few universities, see [1, 2]. Make sure at least two to three professors are available in your choice of research area.

Application mainly needs the following documents before the last date. Additional documents may be needed depending on your nationality and the university you are applying.

(I) Educational Qualification

Most general requirement to apply to US graduate school with a 4-yr bachelor degree or 3-year bachelor degree with master degree in related subject. Most universities require a minimum 3.0 GPA on a 4 point scale. Check your specific qualification details, subject and GPA requirement from the department or university website in which you are applying. If your educational degree has a different grade scale, verify your grades by contacting the graduate school of your every intended university.

(II) Passport

If you are an international student, and you do not have a passport already, then arrange first to proceed. Passport is required to attend GRE, IELTS, TOEFL exams and apply in the graduate school for international applicants. If you have a passport already then check the validity, if your passport is expired, renew it first to proceed. Valid passport will also be required for VISA application after your selection in the graduate school.

(III) GRE General

Graduate Record Examinations (GRE) general test is presently not required for the admission in most of the US universities. But it can be required in some PhD programs. GRE general fee ranges from 220 to 231.30 US Dollar as per July 2023. Details about the test can be found in [3]. Applicants are suggested to verify by the graduate school and department about the requirement of the GRE general test. Content of GRE general test :

- Verbal Reasoning
- Quantitative Reasoning
- Analytical Writing

Some graduate schools require a minimum score on the GRE general test, applicants should verify with each university or department in which you are applying.

(IV) GRE Subject

The GRE subject test is another test conducted only in Mathematics, Physics, and Psychology. At present most graduate schools do not require the subject GRE for the admission. If you are applying to a graduate program in Mathematics, Physics, Psychology. Check directly to your intended university or department about the subject GRE requirement. Fee for the GRE subject is 150 US Dollar as per July 2023. Details about subject GRE can be found in [4].

Some graduate schools require a minimum score on the GRE subject test, applicants should verify with each university or department in which you are applying.

(V) IELTS / TOEFL

The International English Language Testing System (IELTS) or Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL) is required for most international students. Check with the university about the requirements of IELTS or TOEFL. Details about the IELTS test, see [5]. IELTS fee varies with testing location, see [6]. Details about the TOEFL test, see [7]. TOEFL fee also varies with testing location, see [8]. Content of IELTS / TOEFL test :

- Reading
- Writing
- Listening
- Speaking

Graduate schools set a minimum score on IELTS / TOEFL, check details with your intended university. In addition to the minimum score some universities also set a minimum score on the speaking component of IELTS / TOEFL. Depending on your nationality, some graduate schools may not require IELTS / TOEFL.

(VI) Statement of Purpose

Statement of Purpose (SOP) or Personal Statement is required to submit in the application. SOP is an important document for your success in graduate school admission. It is strongly emphasized to the applicants to invest a significant amount of time in writing effective SOP. It is encouraged to read Q&A on statement of purpose with Professor Robert Riehn, North Carolina State University, see [9]. How to write a statement of purpose, read [10, 11, 12].

(VII) Letter of Recommendation

Three letters of recommendation are normally required in graduate school admission. Check the details with the universities you are applying to. It would be good to read the Q&A on how to get great letters of recommendation with Osase Omoruyi, graduate student from Harvard University, see [13]. How to request letters of recommendation, read [14, 15].

(VIII) CV or Resume

CV is required to submit in the graduate school application. Tips for writing an effective CV, read [16, 17].

(IX) Submit Application Form

Most universities normally start accepting applications in September for the admission in the next year fall semester. Last date to submit complete applications normally is 01 December - 15 January. Application fee typically ranges from 50 - 100 US Dollar. Some universities also have an application fee waiver option. Applicants are advised to visit respective departments or graduate schools to find details about waiver options.

Interview

After your application submission, graduate school or department may invite you for the interview with a few faculty members of the department. It is advisable to strongly prepare for the interview. How to prepare for a graduate school interview, read [18, 19, 20, 21].

Offer Letter

Decision of your selection will be informed to you normally before April. Offer letter sent to accepted candidates. You need to accept it before 15 April. Carefully read your offer letter and follow the instructions given. Your reporting date to the university or department is mentioned in a letter. Usually reporting date is August 1 for fall admissions.

GTA / GRA Appointment

Your offer letter shows your appointment as GTA or GRA or GTA-GRA combined. Most students are initially appointed as a graduate teaching assistant (GTA) for the first two years. Subsequently appointed as a graduate research assistant (GRA) after joining a research group in the department.

Stipend

Your offer letter shows your stipend. For example, physics graduate students typically receive an average stipend between 20,000 - 30,000 US Dollar per year depending on the university. Most universities give the stipends on a monthly basis. Stipend is usually given on the last day of each month. Stipend normally starts from August 1 for the admission in the fall semester.

Fees

Your offer letter shows your fees required, if any. Department normally waives the tuition fees and provides health insurance for the graduate students. Graduate school may have some semester fees. Most of the students easily pay from their own stipends.

Transcript

After your acceptance, graduate school instructs you to provide academic transcripts from your university.

US VISA - F1

Accepted international graduate students need a US F1 VISA to enter the United States. You must have a passport already to start the VISA process, arrange first if you do not have it. Graduate school or department will provide instructions for VISA application in the embassy of your home country. Main steps in F1-VISA application process are :

- Receive I-20 Form from the University
- Pay SEVIS I-901 Fee (350 US Dollar as per July 2023)
- Fill VISA Application DS-160
- Pay VISA fee (185 US Dollar as per July 2023)
- VISA Appointment (book early, waiting times can be longer)
- VISA Interview

It is strongly advised to prepare for F1-VISA interview, read [22, 23].

Pre-Arrival Instructions

After obtaining a US F1 VISA sticker on your passport. Universities usually provide detailed pre-arrival instructions. Few considerations in pre-arrival as :

- **Flight Reserve** - Flight must be booked after getting VISA. Plan to land in US at least one or two day before your reporting date.
- **Accommodation Reserve** - Normally needs to pay for the first month rent after booking and security deposit (most places take one month rent), i.e. total pay two month rent
For perspective only : Depending on location, shared apartment rent, averaged per month varies 700 - 1000 US Dollar (as per July 2023).

Most graduate students stay off-campus since universities generally do not provide on-campus accommodation for the grad students. Check with your university for off-campus housing options.

- **Amount Carry** - At least 200 - 300 US Dollar for food etc (as per July 2023), for survival of first month (since your stipend usually comes on last day of a August for fall admissions)
- **Packing** - Check with your university instructions, if any.
- **Departure to United States**

Welcome to United States ! After your landing in the US. You can use Uber/Lyft or call a taxi from airport to your apartment address. Prior inform your apartment office to your arrival.

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About the Author

Ibrahim is a fourth year PhD Physics candidate as a GRA at the University of Tennessee. His research interest is search on neutrinoless double-beta decay process at LEGEND experiment.

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